

An Investigation on the Use of Nutrient-Dense Foods (Nutraceuticals) by the General Public in a Chosen Region in Bangladesh

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Abstract:

Nutraceuticals have a range of biochemical effects on consumers' health. Nutraceuticals have benefits beyond their fundamental nutritional roles. It is critical to distinguish dietary shortages from other physiological impacts, such as decreased risk of disease. Nutraceuticals include things like dietary supplements, refined foods, genetically modified foods, and herbal supplements. A survey on nutritional supplements was carried out in select regions of Bangladesh's Savar. 180 men and women in all were sought out, and most of them went through thorough in-person interviews. This study's main objective was to determine how much information rural and urban populations knew about and used nutritional supplements. The results and discussion section presents and clarifies all of the findings. In summary, this study broadens the current understanding of the pattern of nutraceutical use among Bangladeshi urban and rural populations.

Keywords:

Refined grains, healthy food, Diseases, urban and rural populations, and nutraceuticals

1. Introduction: "Dietary supplements" are the terms used to describe these foods that have medicinal or nutritional significance. Nutraceuticals, which encompass a variety of products such as vitamins, herbal cures, genetically or living modified foods and supplements, as well as everyday things like fortified breakfast cereals and "bio" yoghurts, are also referred to as medicinal foods, functional foods, phytochemicals, and nutritional supplements. Due to the wide range of terms and meanings used in different countries, there may be confusion. A "food, or parts of a food, that provide health benefits, including the prevention and treatment of disease," is how nutraceuticals are often defined (Cencic & Chingwaru, 2010). Nutraceuticals are health-promoting foods that enhance fitness, boost immunity, and improve general well-being, all of which help prevent and treat certain diseases (Dudeja et al., 2016). Numerous nutraceuticals have been demonstrated to play important roles in immune function and potential to specific disease states. Additionally, they reveal conditions like allergies, obesity, Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease, cardiovascular diseases, cancer, and eye disorders that alter indicators linked to oxidative stress (Pandey et al., 2010).

Unprocessed foods that have been given fresh perspectives on their possible health benefits are known as traditional nutraceuticals. In essence, they are unprocessed, entire foods. Not the food

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itself, but the customer's perception of it is the only thing that has changed. Natural components found in a wide variety of fruits, vegetables, cereals, fish, dairy, and meat products have health advantages beyond simple dietary intake. Salmon's omega-3 fatty acids, soy's saponins, and tomatoes' lycopene antioxidant are a few examples of them (Kessler et al., 2001a). Tomatoes and salmon are two foods that researchers have discovered contain nutrients that go beyond basic nutrition – in this case, lycopene and omega-3 fatty acids (Kessler et al., 2001a). Non-traditional nutraceuticals include calcium-fortified orange juice, vitamin-or mineral-fortified cereals, and folic acid-fortified rice. They emerge as a result of agricultural breeding or by adding nutrients and/or ingredients (Hoque, 2023). Scientists studying agriculture have successfully created methods to raise the nutritional content of particular crops. Research is underway on many other crops to improve their nutritional value.

The frequency of micronutrient deficiencies is increasing every day in Bangladesh. A prior study found that 14% of people in Bangladesh between the ages of 15 and 49 experienced chronic energy deficit or malnutrition, while 25% of adults between the ages of 46 and 60 had an undernourished or thin BMI of 18.5 (Karim & Tasnim, 2016; Hoque, 2024; Hoque, 2023). According to a recent study, 70% of patients usually see a doctor either before or during traditional therapy, which suggests that natural therapy is not well-liked (Kessler et al., 2001b). Bangladesh's food system is experiencing fast change. In terms of: (i) market purchases versus own production; (ii) the commodity base of diets; (iii) a long-term tendency towards a growing role of international trade in food commodities, and consequently greater influence of trade policies and international prices on domestic prices; and (iv) more food commodities being processed outside of the immediate producing or consuming households, changes in consumption and expenditure patterns are occurring in both urban and rural areas (Zahirul et al., 2014; Owens et al., 2014). Several studies reveal that people who take nutritional supplements develop a variety of beneficial health-related behaviors, such as improved eating habits, consistent exercise, and upholding a healthy body weight (Bailey et al., 2011).

The current study aims is to determine the population's use, knowledge and awareness of nutritional supplements in a chosen area in Bangladesh.

2. Methodology: This was a field survey which was conducted by semi-structured questionnaire. In this study, data were collected from 180 respondents from different locations throughout the Savar area. The study was carried out between a period of January to February 2024. Participants (age between 18-60 years old) were recruited from selected area. Each participant independently filled out the anonymous questionnaire, providing the most accurate answers they could; some individuals were unable to answer every question. The survey data was computed, reviewed, and graphically presented using Microsoft Office Excel. The

Jahangirnagar University ethical approval committee evaluated this paper and approved it; all respondent data was kept confidential.

Figure 1: Study location in Bangladesh Map (Savar Upazila Bangladesh)

3. Results: All findings and result with percentages from this survey study concluded in table presented below.

Table 1: Demography of respondents

Variable	Response pattern	Number (N=180)	Percent
Age (year)	20 to 39	105	58.33%
	40 to 60	75	41.67%
Gender	Male	97	53.88%
	Female	83	46.12%
Occupation	Students	48	26.66%
	Job holder	33	18.33%
	Housewife	54	30%
	Unemployed	45	25%
Residence	Rural	114	63.33%
	Urban	66	36.67%

Figure 2: Gender distribution among population

Table 2: Most often utilized nutraceuticals among those surveyed

Variable	Number of individuals	Percent
Traditional nutraceuticals	115	63.88%
Non-conventional nutraceuticals	65	36.12%

Table 3: Supplemental usage of nutraceuticals in diet

Variable	Respondents	Percent
Dairy foods	28	15.55%
Grains	15	8.33%
Glucosamine sulfate and chondroitin sulfate	65	36.11%
Different fruit juice	72	40%

Table 4: Nutraceuticals used to alleviate different types of diseases

Variable	Respondents	Percent
Diabetes	16	8.9%
Obesity	70	38.88%
Diarrhea	12	6.67%
Allergy	10	5.55%
Neuro disorder	02	1.11%
Constipation	36	20%
Appetite problem	34	19%

Table 5: Understanding and Observation regarding Daily Consumption of Nutritious Foods

Variable	Response pattern	Frequency (N=180)	Percent
Knowledge	Conscious	112	62.22%
	Unaware/Indifferent	46	25.56%
	No clear response	22	12.10%
Daily consumption of Nutraceuticals and perceptions	Highly sufficient	50	27.76%
	Sufficient	48	26.66%
	Not sufficient	82	45.55%
Different source of information	TV	17	9.44%
	Google	70	38.88%
	Newspaper	41	22.77%
	Friends & family	52	28.88%

4. Discussion: The study was conducted on several town and village of this district with a standard structured questionnaire. In the present work, it observed that a great portion of study population (53.88%) is male. In case of occupation, 18.33% were job holder in different sectors, 30% were housewife and 25% were unemployed, while 26.66% were students. Residents from local village were most in number and shown in terms of percentage shown in (table - 1). On the other hand 115 (63.88%) respondents told that they mostly use conventional (unprocessed) or traditional nutraceuticals while rest of the population 65 (36.12%) informed they use synthetic (processed) or non-conventional nutraceuticals, shown in (table – 2).

Table – 3 represents about different types of nutraceuticals and foods used as nutraceuticals, where most people prefer refined grains (8.33%) and fruit juice (40%) as nutraceuticals. Respondents used nutraceuticals to treat different types of diseases. According to their verses, most people prefer nutraceuticals for the treatment obesity, but it was found that very few people (1.1%) stated that they use it for neurological problems (table – 4).

(Table – 5) explaining about the knowledge, awareness and consumption of nutraceuticals, which not much satisfactory in terms of consumption of enough nutraceutical supplements for better health. It observed that a big portion of the participants about (25.56%) were not aware of the value of daily intake of nutritional foods. Although a sufficient number of population are not aware of nutritional foods, more than half percent (62.22%) respondents are alert of it. Among all the responses (38.88%) respondent stated they gain information from google about nutrition and relevant studies constituting the most percentage of all, whereas, least number of people (9.44%) learned information about nutrition from TV.

In Bangladesh, undernutrition remains a serious public health concern. Although the number of overweight women and children under five is increasing, overnutrition is still not a serious problem. Food insecurity still affects 35% of the population (<https://www.usaid.gov/sites/default/files/documents/>), 600,000 children suffer from severe acute malnutrition (Ricci & Becker, 1996), and 43% of children between the ages of six months

and five suffer from anemia (Grover & Ee, 2009). It is also crucial to look into the effects of different food patterns, morbidity, childcare and feeding habits, access to healthcare, environmental factors, and sociocultural contexts on malnutrition (Hoque et al., 2023; Bhuiya et al., 1986). The interest in this study, which attempts to look at the prevalence of use of nutritional foods as nutraceuticals in Bangladesh and also the depth of knowledge.

5. Conclusion: Nutraceuticals, functional foods, and naturally occurring substances have been the subject of several studies that have examined and reported on their effects. The results have consistently demonstrated these products' high level of activity, considerable impact on cell metabolism, and generally low side effects. It makes natural that in order to preserve their health, people are focusing more on proactive illness prevention. As members of society, it is imperative that we all share information regarding the health problems that the general public faces in order to identify the underlying causes of dietary supplement use and the need for further research. In summary, this study broadens the current understanding of the pattern of nutraceutical use among Bangladeshi urban and rural populations.

Conflict of interest: Author declare that no conflict of interest.

Ethical consideration: Participants actively participated, knowing that any personal information they contributed would be kept private and that the data they provided would be utilized responsibly.

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